

Impacts of Peer-Tutoring-Strategy on Performance and Interest in Biology Concept among Secondary School Students in Katsina State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study assessed the impact of peer tutoring strategy on performance and interest in Biology Concepts among senior secondary school Students in Katsina State, Nigeria. The study was guided by four objectives, corresponding research questions and hypotheses, respectively. The study adopted pretest, post-test quasi experimental design. The population of the study consist of 12176 public senior secondary school class two (SS II) students during the 2024/1025 academic session in Katsina local government area. The sample of the study was 133 selected from the target population using multi-stage sampling technique. Two instruments were explored for the study; LOCPT and LOCII, Reliability index of 0.785 and 0.947, respectively were obtained for using Cronbach Alpha Method. Data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation to answer research questions and while t-test independent sample was used to test all the four hypotheses formulated for the study at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study indicated that peer tutoring strategy has a significant impact on students' academic performance in life organization concepts in biology among senior secondary schools in Katsina State, Nigeria. Based on the findings, the study recommended that, Science Teachers Association of Nigeria (STAN) should train and produce quality teachers that would teach and train teachers through workshop and seminar on peer tutoring strategy at secondary schools, as it enhances students' interest and promote academic performance of both male and female students.

Keywords: Peer tutoring strategy, Academic performance and interest

Introduction

Peer tutoring consists of two or more students' working together, teaching and learning from each other. Peer tutoring involves students' helping other students learn. It offers one on one assistance for students having difficulties in specific subjects. Peer tutoring is the process where the teacher may not be able to give individualized attention to the learners or provide each student in the classroom the opportunity to interact directly with him/her especially in large classes. In large classes for example, it may be extremely difficult for one teacher to meet the individual needs of all students in any lesson. There is simply not enough time on the school time table for the teacher to give sufficient individualized attention to every student each single day. In peer tutoring the brighter students or fast learners are made to teach (tutor) the less bright or slow learners particular biology concepts. Peer tutoring provides small group, intense, focused instruction that allows students' opportunity for active interaction among themselves and by doing so learn from their peers (Abrami, Poulsea & Chambers, 2004; Horvath, 2011).

In peer tutoring strategy, students constitute a huge part of the whole process. The students' can prepare instructional materials as well as receive immediate feedback from their peers. Peer Tutoring is a gateway to review information and practice skills in the classroom. It a teaching intervention strategy in which students' alternate between the role of tutor and tutee. Students' get to be the learner and the teacher! It allows each of the students to have the chance to teach a review lesson, monitor other students in the group, and evaluate each other's work through observations or work samples. Peer tutoring strategy provides small group, intense and focused instruction that allows students the opportunity for active interaction among themselves and by so doing learn from their peers (Abrami, Poulsea & Chambers, 2004; Hovart, 2011; Topping, 2005).

Palincsar (1986) believes that the purpose of peer tutoring teaching is to facilitate a group effort between teacher and students' as well as among students in the task of bringing meaning to a text. Peer tutoring is a contemporary application of Vygotsky's theories; it is used to improve students' ability to learn from texts. In this method, teacher and students collaborate in learning and practicing four key skills: summarizing, questioning, clarifying, and predicting. The teacher's role in the process is reduced over time. Also, peer tutoring is relevant to instructional concepts such as "scaffolding" and "apprenticeship", in which a teacher or more advanced peer helps to structure or arrange a task so that a novice can work on it successfully. Academic performance is referred to as the knowledge attained or skills developed in school subjects, usually determined by test score or marks assigned by the teacher (Miller Kohler, 1993; Topping & Bryce, 2004). Achievement is a result-oriented construct that shows extent of attainment in learning task. It is used to ascertain the extent to which programmed goals are realized (Horvath, 2011; Spencer, 2006).

One of the persistent problems associated with students' academic performance as observed by Adeyemi and popoola (2010), bears on the view that students do not retain the knowledge, skills and ideas acquired during learning for a long time; as such, our teachers should take it seriously into considerations that the Cardinal objective of Nigeria educational system is to produce learners who can retain and use what they have learned in the school and outside the school. This development has therefore, called for the use of different innovative teaching techniques and resources to improve learners' academic performance. Interest is a powerful motivational process that energizes learning, guides academic and career trajectories, and is essential to academic success. Interest is both a psychological state of attention toward a particular object or topic, and an enduring predisposition to reengage over time. Interest is an outcome of experience rather than an inherited tendency towards a certain preference (Kohler et al, 2001). Scheifele (1991) took a different position to this. He defines interest as a content specific motivation, made up of distinct emotive, cognitive and value related domains directed with an organized force towards a purpose. The low level of students' attainment in WAEC in Biology from 2018 to 2022 has given biology educators a high level of concern, which is so because of the universally held assumption of the growth and development of mankind. Research studies (Ibe & Nwosu, 2003; Okoli, 2006; Okoli & Egbunomu, 2011) have indicated that academic performance of students in biology is relatively poor. The performance of candidates in biology for five years; 2018 to 2022 are 79%, 65%, 66%, 71% and 70% respectively; these indicated that there is an issue in teaching the subject (Joda, 2019).

Difficult concepts in life organization (cell, tissue, organ, system, organism and ecosystem) and other difficult concepts in biology syllabus are the reasons why students failed biology in WAEC, the poor performance could be from different methods of teaching life organization in biology which includes hand-on activities, experimental strategy, concept mapping, field trip, storyline as recommended by National Curriculum Council (2023). Poor teaching aids, poor evaluation strategy makes students to failed biology in WAEC. The researcher wants to investigate and find suitable pedagogical strategies to the problem for students to pass their WAEC examination.

Therefore, there is need to search for more effective instructional strategies that are likely to improve students' academic achievement in secondary schools in biology. Hence this study seeks to make a comparative analysis of reciprocal peer tutoring type of cooperative based learning instructional strategy and traditional teaching method in relation to biology achievement among students in senior secondary schools in katsina local government.

In the traditional method of teaching, teaching happens within the four walls of the classroom. Here, the teacher is the sole source of knowledge. It's a teacher-centric method that promotes the supremacy of the teacher within the classroom setup. Also, every aspect of learning proceeds as per his will. The teacher fulfils these functions: Has full control over the learning environment, decides the teaching methodology, determines the course curriculum. In all these circumstances students' interests are relegated to the background, and not considered during classroom pedagogy.

The traditional method of teaching presupposes when a teacher directs students to learn through memorization and recitation techniques thereby not developing their critical thinking problem solving and decision-making skills and interests (Ibraheem Kadhom, 2017) In the traditional method of teaching, teachers followed the drill and rote method of memorization. In this method, children learn through repetition and memorization. There is little or no scope for critical thinking.

The traditional approach to teaching fails in knowledge transfer and transfer of power from the teacher (teacher-centered) to students' (student-centered), and the students are unable to move the knowledge they have acquired in the school to outside the classroom. Moreover, traditional approaches cannot create a link between the syllabi, the real world, and learning.

Thus Ezema (2014), Umar (2015) and Tukur (2021) held that the classroom usage of lecture method is often responsible for learner low- interest and poor academic performance in a variety of subjects including biology. The method discourages open questioning, inquiry and active participation of students and makes the learning of a variety of subject areas difficult and boring. There is, therefore, the felt need to improve on the teaching and learning of biology through the exploration and employment of the use of innovative teaching methods that are learner -Centered since it is believed that meaningful

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teaching could be as a result of active participation by students. Many studies (Ezema, 2021; Umar, 2015; Tukur, 2021; Anselm, 2010; Ibe & Nwosu, 2000; Okoli, 2006; Okoli & Egbunomu, 2011) have been carried out on some innovative methods such as cooperative teaching strategy, concept mapping strategy, discovery strategy, animated media strategy, game and simulation methodology. Evidence from these researchers have shown that these methods are students centered methods of teaching and can enhance learning and performance in a variety of subjects areas among students. Thus, against this back-drop, the researcher intends to investigate the impact of peer -tutoring strategy on students' performance and interest in biology in senior secondary schools in Katsina State, Nigeria.

Objectives of the study

The general objective of this research is to investigate the impact of peer tutoring strategy on students' performance and interest in Biology in senior secondary schools in Katsina state, Nigeria.

Specifically, the objectives of the study were;

1. To Determine the mean academic performance scores of students taught life organization concept using peer-tutoring strategy and those exposed to lecture teaching method in Katsina State.
2. To Determine the mean interest scores of students taught life organization concept using peer-tutoring strategy and those exposed to lecture teaching method in Katsina State.

Research Questions

The following research question guided the study;

1. What is the difference in the mean academic performance scores of biology students taught life organization concepts using peer tutoring strategy and those exposed to lecture teaching method in Katsina State?
2. What is the impact of peer tutoring strategy on biology students' interest in mastering life organization concepts and those exposed to lecture teaching method in Katsina State?

Research Hypotheses

The following Hypotheses are formulated to guide the study, and they include:

H₀₁: There is no significant difference in the mean academic performance scores of biology students' taught life organization concepts using peer tutoring strategy and those exposed to lecture teaching method in Katsina State, Nigeria.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference in the impact of peer tutoring strategy on Biology students' interest in mastering life organization concepts and those exposed to lecture teaching method in Katsina State

Methodology

The design adopted for the study is pretest -posttest quasi- experimental design. Two groups (Experimental and Control) were involved. The experimental group were taught using peer tutoring strategy while the control group were taught using lecture method. the population of the study consists of twelve thousand one hundred and seventy-six (12176) class two (SSII) Biology students during the 2024/2025 academic session in Katsina local government, a sample size of 133 students were selected from the target population using multi-stage sampling technique.

The information collected at the pilot testing stage were subjected to Cronbach Alpha Method. Hence, reliability coefficients of 0.785 and 0.947 were obtained for LOCPT and LOCII, respectively, these indices showed that the instruments are reliable for the study. Descriptive statistics mean and standard deviation were used in answering research questions, Hypotheses were tested using t-test independent samples and Man-Whitney(U-test). All hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. SPSS version 20 was used to process the data.

Result

Research Question One: What is the difference in the mean academic performance scores of biology students' taught life organization concepts using peer tutoring strategy and those exposed to lecture teaching method in Katsina State?

The descriptive statistics in form of mean and standard deviation were used to answer question two and it is presented in Table 1

Table1: Mean academic performance of Biology students taught using Peer Tutoring Strategy and traditional method

Group	N	Mean	S.D	Std. Error	Mean Difference
Experimental	112	22.29	10.980	1.038	7.84
Control	121	14.45	4.701	0.427	

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Table 1 above shows that, the students taught using traditional method of teaching have mean academic performance score of 14.45 with standard deviation of 4.701 whereas the students taught using Peer Tutoring Strategy have mean academic performance score of 22.29 with standard 10.980. This gives the mean academic performance difference of 7.84 in favour of the experimental group.

Research Question Two: What is the impact of peer tutoring strategy on Biology students' interest in mastering life organization concepts and those exposed to lecture teaching method in Katsina State?

The descriptive statistics in the form of mean and mean ranks were used to answer question one and it is presented in Table 2

Table 2: Mean and Mean Rank interest of Biology students taught using peer tutoring strategy and traditional method

Group	N	Mean	Mean rank	Mean Difference
Experimental	112	177.50	19880.00	117.5
Control	121	60.0	7381.00	

Table 2 revealed that mean interest between Biology students was statistically lower in the control group (60.0) as compared to those in the experimental group (177.5). This gives the mean difference of 117.5 in favour of experimental group. The null hypotheses formulated for the purpose of this research were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

Hypothesis testing

Null Hypothesis One: There is no significant difference in the mean academic performance scores of biology students' taught life organization concepts using peer tutoring strategy and those exposed to lecture teaching method in Katsina State
To test H_{01} , post-test scores of the experimental and control groups were subjected to t-test independent sample. Summary of the analysis is shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Independent Samples t-test of the Mean Academic performance Scores of Experimental and Control groups

Control	N	Mean	SD	t-cal	df	p-value	Decision
Experimental	112	22.29	10.980	6.986	231	.000	Significant
Control	121	14.45	4.701				

Table 3 shows the independent sample t-test analyses for post-test mean academic performance scores of control and experimental groups. It shows that, the t-calculated = 6.986, degree of freedom = 231 and observed p-value was 0.000. Since the observed-value was 0.000, which is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis which stated that, 'there is no significant difference in the mean academic performance scores of biology students' taught life organization concepts using peer tutoring strategy and their counterparts taught the same concepts using traditional method among senior secondary schools in Katsina State, Nigeria is hereby rejected. Hence, there was a significant difference in the mean academic performance scores of biology students' taught life organization concepts using peer tutoring strategy and their counterparts taught the same concepts using traditional method among senior secondary schools in Katsina State, Nigeria.

Null Hypothesis Two: There is no significant difference in the impact of peer tutoring strategy on Biology students' interest in mastering life organization concepts and those exposed to lecture teaching method in Katsina State
To test H_{02} , Students' interest scores of the experimental and control groups were subjected to Mann Whitney U-test. Summary of the analysis is shown in Table 4

Table 4: Summary of Mann-Whitney U-test on Interest scores of Students exposed peer tutoring strategy and Traditional Method

Groups	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	Mann Whitney U	Z-value	P value	Decision
Experimental	112	177.50	19880.00	.000	-13.186	.000	Significant
Control	121	61.00	7381.00				

Table 4 shows the Mann Whitney analysis of the mean rank scores of students taught life organization concepts using peer tutoring strategy and those taught using Traditional method. The result shows the observed p-value is 0.00. Since the p-value (0.000) is less than alpha value (0.05), therefore, the null hypothesis one which states that, 'there is no significant difference in the impact of peer tutoring strategy on Biology students' interest in mastering life organization concepts and their counterparts taught the same concepts using traditional method among senior secondary schools in Katsina State, Nigeria is hereby rejected. This shows that, there was a significant difference in the impact of peer tutoring strategy on Biology students'

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interest in mastering life organization concepts and their counterparts taught the same concepts using traditional method among senior secondary schools in Katsina State, Nigeria.

Summary of Findings

Based on the outcome of the analysis, the following are the major findings from the study. There was a significant difference in the mean academic performance scores of biology students' taught life organization concepts using peer tutoring strategy and those exposed to lecture teaching method in Katsina State? There is impact in peer tutoring strategy on Biology students' interest in mastering life organization concepts and those exposed to lecture teaching method in Katsina State?

Conclusion

From the findings of the study and the discussions that followed, the following conclusions were made: Intervention using peer tutoring strategy significantly improved the academic performance of Senior Secondary Schools biology students. The students exposed to peer-tutoring strategy demonstrated significantly better performance and higher scores than those in the control group, who were taught using the traditional teaching method, indicating the effectiveness of peer tutoring in improving performance of biology students. Gender had significant influence on biology students' performance. In other words, male perform significantly better than female counterpart students from the treatment.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Training in peer tutoring strategy is effective in enhancing students' academic performance. Therefore, emphasis should be given to equipping students with the necessary skills in using the strategy.
2. Training in peer tutoring strategy is effective in enhancing students' interest. Therefore, emphasis should be given to equipping students with the necessary skills in using the strategy.
3. Male and female students should be exposed to training in reciprocal peer tutoring strategy without discrimination, since the evidence is that the use of the strategy significantly improves student's academic performance

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